

Lab Report: Control of Bacterial Growth

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Laboratory Control of Bacterial Growth

Abstract

There are several methods of controlling bacterial growth, such as the differential staining methods which encompasses the Gram staining of the cell wall structure. It differentiates the cell wall structure, the endospore Staining, also referred to as spore production in which steam is used to force the primary stain into the spore. The capsule Staining, also is known as capsule production, where extracellular capsule made up of polysaccharides or polypeptides is resistant to stains. Making slides first and allowing to air dry while performing other tasks, using more comfortable to use plate culture on a drop of water, and not using a drop of water if you take a broth culture loop make the staining procedure successful. Instead, spreading the culture thin to air dry quickly, recording colors seen, shape and arrangement of cells, measuring cell length, and working with a staining tray. This lab report mirrors the control of bacteria's growth using the Kirby-Bauer test antibiotic susceptibility, also known as the disk diffusion.

Laboratory Control of Bacterial Growth

Introduction

Early civilizations controlled microbial growth by salting, pickling, drying, and food exposure, and clothing to the sun (Cho et al., 2019). The contamination of surgical wounds was prevented using aseptic techniques developed in the 1800s by Semmelweis and Lister. Before that, nosocomial infections killed over 10% of surgery patients, and 25% of mothers were delivered in the hospital. Some of these methods have evolved and advanced and are being used today. Several methods of controlling bacterial growth include the differential staining methods and the capsule staining or capsule production. This lab report emulates the control of bacteria's growth using the Kirby-Bauer test antibiotic susceptibility, also known as the disk diffusion. Control of microorganisms' growth is essential in contamination prevention, stopping the spread of disease and infection, and reducing food spoilage. Using physical or chemical agents allows for the control of microbial growth. Physical control is achieved by heat, radiation, or filtration (Prest, 2016). Chemical control is achieved by many different natural and synthetic agents, including antibiotics, bleach, ethanol, hydrogen peroxide, and more. Various bacteria can require other control methods depending on the cell wall structure, presence of a spore, location, and more.

The antibiotic susceptibility test is the most widely used to determine the antibiotic choice for an infection. The method is dependent on bacterial growth inhibition measured through standard conditions. The Mueller-Hinton agar culture medium is uniformly and aseptically inoculated with the organism on the test, and filter disks entirely concentrated with an antibiotic are put on the medium. The organism grows on the agar plate as the antibiotic inhibits its growth. There will be no growth if the organism is susceptible to the antibiotic. The inhibition

zone is observed and measured to determine the organism's susceptibility to the antibiotic (Nguyen, 2017). The measurement is compared using a criterion that classifies the organism as resistant, intermediate, or susceptible.

Materials and Methods

Gram Staining

- Crystal violet (1 min) rinsed with water, iodine as mordant (1 min) rinsed with water, decolorize (~20 sec) rinsed with water, counterstain with safranin (~50 sec) rinsed with water, and blot dry
- gram-positive cells keep purple crystal violet, and gram-negative cells are reddish-pink with safranin
- slides were made first and allowed to air dry while you perform other tasks
- Easier to use plate culture on a drop of water; do not use a drop of water if you take a loop of broth culture instead, Spread the culture thin to air dry quickly
- Record color (s) seen, shape and arrangement of cells and measure cell length
- Always work over a staining tray
- Liquid waste is poured into a chemical waste jug in the fume hood
- Paper square in a solid waste beaker with an orange biohazard bag

Kirby-Bauer test antibiotic susceptibility by disk diffusion

- A swab is used to coat the whole surface of the agar plate with the pure culture of the bacteria
- Antibiotic disks are placed on the surface of the bacterial lawn.
- The antibiotic will diffuse into the agar, with the lowest concentration being the farthest from the disk.

- The inhibition zone around the disk is due to the lack of bacteria growth in that area inhibited by the antibiotic.
- The zone's diameter is measured and compared to known standards to interpret if the bacteria are sensitive or resistant to the antibiotic.

Kirby-Bauer Procedure Antibiotic Disk Susceptibility

- Label two 100mm Mueller-Hinton plates with group #, date, MH, organism (*E. coli* or *B. subtilis*)
- Use 24 hr culture broth
- Use only ONE cotton swab to spread 24hr culture on two 100mm MH plates
- Completely cover plates with culture and let sit with the lid on for 2-3 minutes
- Use tweezers (flamed and cooled) to place three different discs on each swabbed plate
- Leave upright for a couple of minutes, then parafilm
- Measure diameter (mm) of clearing compare to Table 2.2 to indicate if bacteria are resistant, susceptible, or intermediate

Interpretation

The sizes of zones, especially the area of no growth around the disk, are measured using a template or a ruler in millimeters. The results are interpreted as sensitive, resistant, and intermediate for each antimicrobial concerning the ranges listed on the enteric gram-negative rods. The metric ruler is used to measure the zone of inhibition in light. If there is no zone at all, it is reported as 0, even if the disc is around 7mm. The reporting of the diameter of the area is done in millimeters, checked on chart, and recorded as intermediate, resistant, and sensitive.

Results

Gram Stain

The images captured after the gram stain procedure were viewed through the microscope. There was a green hue on the images of *E. coli* and *B. subtilis*. The green hue is a remnant that is removed by lighting and focus adjustment. The final color was recorded after the completion of the Gram stain procedure. The stains were pink and purple. The length was measured and sizes calculated and the shapes and arrangements were also recorded.

Kirby-Bauer

The results of the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion test were done in two groups and the diameter of each antibiotic clearing for *E. coli* and *subtilis* were measured.

The diameter of clearing measurements for the Kirby-Bauer Test

<i>Antibiotic</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E.coli</i>
Chloramphenicol	24 mm	24 mm
Moxalactam	0 mm	9 mm
Penicillin G	33 mm	34 mm
Polymyxin B	16 mm	15 mm
Streptomycin	26 mm	30 mm
Vancomycin	23 mm	22 mm

When measuring, the diameter of the disk was included

Zone Size Interpretive Chart for Bauer-Kirby Test

Antimicrobial agent	R= mm or less	I = mm	S= mm or more
Amoxicillin (20 mcg) with Clavulanic Acid (10 mcg)	14	15-16	20
Bacitracin 10 units	8	9-12	13

Chloramphenicol (30mcg)	12	13-17	18
Ciprofloxacin	15	16-20	21
Clindamycin	14	15-20	21
Colistin (10 mcg)	8	9-10	11
Erythromycin (15 mcg)	13	14-22	23
Moxalactam (30 mcg)	14	15-22	23
Nalidixic Acid	13	14-18	19
Penicillin (10 units)	28	-	29
Polymyxin B	8	9-11	12
Streptomycin (10 mcg)	11	12-14	15
Sulfisoxazole (aka Sulphafurazole) (300 µg)	12	13-16	17
Tetracycline (30 µg)	14	15-18	19
Trimethoprim (5 µg)	10	11-15	16
Vancomycin (30 mcg)	9	10-11	12

Source: Laboratory results data.

Bleach Effects

After swabbing each plate, disk containing filter papers with a arrange of bleach solution concentrations was subjectd on each plate for at least 10 minutes. They were then removed and the plates subjctd to incubationfor 48 hours. The clearing diameter was measured and recorded in the case of each plate.

The clearing diameter results were as follows.

Concentration of bleach *B. subtilis* *E. coli*

0% bleach (control)	0 mm	0 mm
0.01% bleach	5 mm	0 mm
0.1% bleach	7 mm	7 mm
0.25% bleach	9 mm	9 mm
0.5% bleach	11 mm	11 mm

Effects of temperature

After the 48 hours elapsed, the both culture was placed under each temperature for 10 minutes from the 40°C to the 100°C. Before the both culture ws move to higher temperatures, a simple steak was done on the agar plate. The growth amount on the plate was measured and recorded after the 48 hour incubation time elapsed.

Amount of growth on an agar plate after 10 minutes in each temperature

	40°C	60°C	80°C	100°C
<i>B. subtilis</i>	+++	+++	+++	-
<i>E. coli</i>	+++	++	+	-

Discussion and Literature

B. subtilis shows high rates of resistance to chloramphenicol, penicillin, Streptomycin, Streptomycin and Vancomycin while and sensitive on Moxalactam an intermediate on Polymyxin B. *E. coli* showed the same type of results as it was resistance to chloramphenicol, penicillin, Streptomycin, Streptomycin and Vancomycin while and sensitive on Moxalactam an intermediate on Polymyxin B. Therefore, Moxalactam is considered appropriate for empirical treatment of *E. coli* in this area of study. It is recommended that the antimicrobial susceptibility be regularly monitored.

The study's findings indicated that *E. coli* and related strains had the potential to form microfilms and had resistance to antibiotics, which could be related to information potency. In a study that aimed to build up a biological control method for bacterial contamination removal by small size ciliate, Cho et al. (2019) posits that ciliate reduce cholera's bacterial population. In another study to determine the resistance of *Coomonas testosterone* to drugs by K-B method, Nguyen et al. (2017) found the results consistent with this study by positing that the interpretative results of the *C. testosterone* should not be reported but the test results.

References

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